

LIVED EXPERIENCES OF THE DEPARTMENT OF TRADE AND INDUSTRY SMALL MEDIUM ENTERPRISE ROVING ACADEMY RECIPIENTS: A PHENOMENOLOGICAL APPROACH

Mark Angelo B. Laviste

SDO Camarines Norte, Department of Education, Daet, Camarines Norte, Philippines

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14328571>

ABSTRACT

This research study aimed to analyze the experiences of Small Medium Enterprise Academy Recipients in Daet, Camarines Norte to improve the program. The study used a qualitative method with a survey questionnaire and Thematic Analysis to gather data. The findings revealed that most SMEs have sufficient knowledge in managing their businesses, but some are new to the field. They use social media platforms for selling and earning money, contribute to their community, and make customer satisfaction. Some have trust in themselves, while others struggle with capital. Most SMEs are sole proprietorships with 1-2.5 employees and experience in selling products and services. The survey questionnaires reveal that the lived experience of SMEs has strong effects on their competitive advantage, innovative systems, financial matters, quality products, low manufacturing costs, and timely financial reports. However, some SMEs face challenges in implementation due to personal issues, conflict of interest, and inadequate resources. Recommendations include adapting information from other countries, screening program recipients, outsourcing cost-effective products or materials, creating a policy supporting SMEs with financial help, increasing collaboration with government, private agencies, and educational institutions, and conducting future studies on the lived experiences of SMEs to better understand their needs in producing quality products and services, effective financial information, and decision-making.

Keywords: *Lived experiences, social media platforms, selling, earning money, customer satisfaction, quality products, manufacturing costs, financial reports, challenges, decision-making*

INTRODUCTION

Department of Trade and Industry is one of the government offices that serves the people and shares knowledge to enable them to become productive. DTI is the primary government division in charge of managing, promoting, facilitating, and executing regulators on trade, and investment within the nation. Its main function was to foster and accelerate the expansion of the nation's already strong and prosperous sectors Presidential Decree 488 (June 21, 1974). It continues the government's initiatives to bolster the nation's socio-economic growth, especially in commerce. Additionally, it created the Bureau of Foreign Trade to promote domestic marketing and trade initiatives through Presidential Decree 721 (June 2, 1975). The said office has developed training programs for the starting entrepreneur and soon the future of the business world. One of their programs is the SME Roving Academy, which was crafted with the help of MSMEs and other national and sub-national stakeholders. Its main objective is to give entrepreneurs knowledge in doing business such as managerial capabilities, marketing strategy, and law and regulation.

The shift of businesses today is more drastic wherein they need to continue their improvement to meet the needs and demands of their clients to sustain their operations. Gaining new knowledge on how to handle business, adapt to the changes, and make a strong marketing strategy to increase the number of customers is a must to learn and implement to survive the competition. As time goes by, innovations and strategies in selling products and services have been discovered because of the experiences of entrepreneurs. The experiences they have been through give them the idea to correct their mistakes and make a new strategy to survive. Training for business owners and their staff needs to be done in this new era of growing businesses because of the competition in their field to continue their operation. Micro Small and Medium Enterprises increased the total number of employments in all countries, it serves as the main foundation of the economic profitability.

The Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) contribution to global growth development is significant and is substantial in employment creation. The more business entities are established; the more management of resources will be required to enhance firm revenue. Accounting information is reliable and fast-based financial reporting is necessary to obtain optimum revenue outcomes in terms of reporting the firm's operational wealth in the millennial age. The improvement of information technology resulted in the progress of a business accounting information system that is centered on competitive advantage (Asmuni, 2020). It is also one of the government's priorities, as asserted in the 2017 to 2022 Philippine Development Plan (PDP) in Chapter 9: Using Trabaho and Negosyo to increase economic opportunities in industry and services. According to Philippine Development Plan PDP (2017), one of the challenges faced by MSMEs is statistics on integration and support because they are inadequate. These were required to monitor sector performance and to provide a foundation for strategic planning. Enhancing access to technology and innovation via promoting innovation and technology adoption is one of the solutions mentioned by National Economic Development Authority (2018).

The Philippine government has allocated money and time to support its local entrepreneurs in showcasing their products and building a strong foundation in the field. SME Roving Academy is one of the government's programs under the Department of Trade and Industry or DTI, it has been serving businesses for almost 8 years. It enables them to learn of the various procedures in proper handling of a business to prosper and become stable in the field. The Department of Trade and Industries states that MSMEs were categorized according to their asset size (excluding land) and number of employees. MSMEs are defined in accordance with assets by the Magna Carta Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (R.A. No. 6977, as amended). They are the engine of economic growth in the country comprising 99.58 percent (1,080,810) of business establishments and only 0.42 percent or 4,531 are large enterprises as per PSA 2021 List of Establishments. Also, as per the Department of Interior and Local Government gathered data from LGUs there were 2,081,274 million registered enterprises in the country as of August 31, 2021 (Department of Trade and Industries).

Different kinds of training were needed by MSMEs in the field of Financing, Marketing, Compliance with Government Regulations, Skill/Management Training, and Technology Upgrading DTI Impact Assessment Surveys of Covid-19 on the MSME Sector (September 16-30, 2021). MSMEs create pathways to the goals of every person involved in its operation. In ASEAN, there are 70 million Micro, Small, and Medium-Sized businesses, which creates 97.2 percent - 99.9 percent of total businesses in the ASEAN Constituent States. Micro small and medium enterprises often constitute the biggest share of business. The MSMEs contributed up to 85 percent to the employment and GDP at 44.8 percent and national exports at 18 percent (ASEAN, 2020). An entrepreneur must be equipped with knowledge that can uphold their business to the top of their respective field. Resmi et al. (2021) said that taxes were viewed as expenses, lowering net income. On the other hand, to apply for specific bank loans and get government incentive funding, financial reports and tax expertise were necessary. The MSMEs understand the importance of financial and tax reports since they have received training in their preparation. Completing tax returns SPT, NPWP, and financial reports are the things that can help their firm run better. The SMEs' problems can be attributed to a lack of an accountable and effective accounting system, the low educational experience of operators, and the hiring of unskilled accounting employees, both of which contribute to misleading accounting or financial statements (Rustiana and Khairunnisa, 2019).

Training can help a business to accomplish its goals and serve its clients well. The world of business today has been continuously changing due to the needs of their customers. Moreover, building a business along with the other established businesses could lead them to subside early in the competition because of not having a good production plan. An increasing market rivalry, customers' expectations, and unpredicted issues in business are some of the reasons why a starting business collapses. Therefore, the Philippine government was encouraged to take a thorough and coordinated strategy to ensure the SMEs' indisputable success. Infrastructure, product expansion, financing, and marketing training, along with other efforts, are all covered under the policy. Republic Act 9501, previously known as the Magna Carta for Small Enterprises (Republic Act 6977), was adopted by the government to provide guidance and encouragement for the growth of

micro, small and medium-sized businesses. This law establishes the broad rules that shape the improvement of micro, small, and medium-sized businesses.

Hence, this study will be conducted to gather data about the Lived Experiences of the Department of Trade and Industry Small Medium Enterprise Roving Academy Recipients. Moreover, it will investigate the issues encountered by MSMEs in their training and the possible action plan to improve the implementation of the said program above.

Research Questions

This study seeks to gather data about the Lived Experiences of the Department of Trade and Industry Small Medium Enterprise Roving Academy Recipients.

Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. How may the lived experiences of the key informants be described before the DTI SME Roving Academy program was introduced in terms of their:
 - 1.1 personal lives;
 - 1.2 social aspects; and
 - 1.3 economic circumstances?
2. What are the challenges faced by the program's beneficiaries upon its introduction encompassing aspects of their:
 - 2.1 personal lives;
 - 2.2 social aspects; and
 - 2.3 economic circumstances?
3. How does the DTI SME Roving Academy as a program changes the lives of the program beneficiaries along:
 - 3.1 personal lives;
 - 3.2 social aspects; and
 - 3.3 economic circumstances?
4. Based on the program experiences, what improvements may be recommended to enhance the implementation of DTI SME Roving Academy?

METHODOLOGY

The researcher of this study utilized the Qualitative method of research. As stated by Jeff Brown (2020), qualitative research is a method that shows the features of the population or phenomena being studied. The said method focused on providing a comprehensive understanding based on the collected data. Thus, the qualitative research method was used because the study searched for answers about the profile of Small and Medium Enterprises about the number of workers, managerial capabilities, marketing strategy, technology used, business licensing knowledge, type of business, main product, target buyers, assets size classification, and the risk tolerance. Additionally, the study searched for answers about the effect of SME Roving Academy on the SME's growth and challenges encountered in the implementation of the program.

Research Locale

There was a total of ten SMEs interviewed based on the number of SMEs provided by the DTI-Daet per the study's description of the respondents which the researcher intends to cover in his study to answer the questions in the SOP and then to showcase their experiences in a business, particularly to those who were just starting. And also, to further provide possible actions to promote the development of the program and the growth of the business.

Participants of the Study

The respondents were the Small and Medium Enterprises operating in Daet, Camarines Norte, and duly registered in the Department of Trade and Industry (DTI) in 2018. They were varied in the kind of business, total number of workers, form of ownership, main products, target buyers, and the assess size classification. Categorically, the respondents were those who had been continuously in operation for at least five (5) years based on the Department of Trade and Industry. The eligible respondents were the SME recipients in Daet, Camarines Norte. These SMEs were operating their business in their respective fields with minimal information on the proper handling of business. They have been selected to attend the said program of DTI to learn more knowledge to apply in their day-to-day operation. They were described with their profile on name, sex, products or services, and number of years in the field. Respondents were only the recipients of the program in this survey.

Research Instrument

The primary data collection tool for the research was an interview guide researcher-made questionnaire. The tool was used to open the way for the data used in the study. The research questionnaire was separated into three sections and differs based on the details required for the analysis. The first part was the SMEs' profile type of business, total number of employees, managerial capabilities, marketing strategy, technology used, business licensing knowledge, type of business, main products, target buyers, and the assess size classification and risk tolerance. The second part was about the SME Roving Academy and its effect on its growth. The third section was the challenges faced in the implementation of the said program above. The researcher-made questionnaire went through a series of evaluations to ensure the data collected were right and answer correctly all the queries of this study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher's adviser and members of the thesis advisory committee reviewed the researcher-made interview guide questionnaire. It was subjected to the requisite checks on the relevance and meaning of the claims to ensure that the data collected is vital to the aims and objectives of the analysis. The researcher-made questionnaire was checked and scrutinized by the thesis advisory committee. Then, after thorough checking, to know the usability and accuracy of the questionnaire. This activity showed the consistency of

the queries, factors, and measures inside the questionnaire and was utilized to identify potential questionnaire mistakes as well as to verify the questionnaire's validity. Afterward, it was distributed to the respondents. First, the researcher gave a request letter for the owner/manager's approval to conduct data gathering. Once approved, informed consent was provided along with the interview guide questionnaire to the respondents. It was collected, grouped, and analyzed to produce concrete and accurate results. The researcher guaranteed that the data collected were exclusively for academic purposes and held strictly confidential. The college's ethical protocols in research were strictly followed.

Data Analysis

The data obtained in this study was assessed and interpreted utilizing Thematic Analysis. This method was primarily used to analyze data through sets of information and create patterns from the data to find themes. Using this kind of technique, one can easily interpret the data gathered in an interview. In this type of treating data, the interviewer identified what code or theme was tapped to have a clear interpretation. This study collected data about the experiences of small businesses. It includes their experiences from the start of their business to the implementation of the program they underwent in the Department of Trade and Industry. The collected data answers the primary goals of this study. The collected data was grouped and analyzed based on the responses of the participants to ensure the concreteness of the results.

Scope and Limitation

This research described the lived experiences of Department of Trade and Industry Small Medium Enterprise Roving Academy recipients in Daet, Camarines Norte, and its implication to their growth. This research would lead to the determination of the Small and Medium Enterprises profile regarding their experiences before and after the implementation of SME Roving Academy. Also, the implication of SME Roving Academy in their start-up stage, marketing awareness, marketing readiness, and export readiness, the challenges encountered in the execution of SME Roving Academy, and the proposed action plan to improve the SME Roving Academy and contribute to the growth of the business.

There were ten (10) respondents interviewed from the total population of the Micro Small and Medium Enterprises in Daet, Camarines Norte that was requested from the Department of Trade and Industry. This study was limited to collecting data on the respondents in terms of their personal lives, social aspects, and economic circumstances. Its main purpose was to collect data based on their experiences before undertaking training, during the training, and after. The data were gathered and collected based on a research-made interview guide. The researcher ensured that the data collected was used exclusively for academic purposes and held strictly confidential. The college's ethical protocols for the research were strictly followed.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This presents the findings from the data analysis to provide a thorough explanation of the themes that emerged in response to the study's aims, discussions are also included.

Lived experiences of the Key Informants before the DTI SME Roving Academy Program was Introduced

Personal Lives. The analysis of the data generated two categories of the challenges of SMEs in their personal lives before undergoing the training. These are production and management, and under each category are the specific challenges experienced by the SMEs. To refer to the participants' quoted answers to the interview, "R" for responses is used with its corresponding number as seen in the appendices.

The first category of challenges experienced by the SMEs is capital. Capital is the amount of money wherein without or lacking this could give a lot of problems for the owners. In some businesses, their capital is the most vital for the continuation of their goals. Businesses are expected to give the best to their customers, good products or services that make them satisfied. However, small businesses have limited resources only and sometimes they cannot afford to buy a large number of materials because of the small earnings they have. They roll the money or earnings for the next day of selling. Most of the SMEs' problem in production and selling is their capital. That is why most of them shared their taught in how they manage their business. Key Informant number 1 says *"May maisave lang ako sa gasul sa lending parang rolling ko lang"* (I can only save something for gasul and lending like I'm just rolling). It only means that most small businesses earn a small amount only and they use it to survive their daily lives.

Also, Key Informant number 3 states *"Ako kasi by order lang"* (I'm just by order). Most of the owner of small businesses often do their products only if someone is ordering from them. From that order, they can buy materials for their production. Likewise, Key Informant number 4 says *"Yung kita ibibili"* (The income I will use to buy). It has something to do with the income that they use to roll as a new budget for the next day. The small amount they earn every single day will be added to their capital to buy more ingredients to produce more products to sell. Most of the successful businesses also came with a small capital and they just rolled the income to allocate for production. In addition, Key Informant number 5 says *"Pag may puhunan lang ako makakatinda"* (I can only sell if I have the capital). Those earnings they get from selling their products are going to be used in buying additional ingredients for possible more productions. Most of the small businesses cannot continue their business every day because of a lack of capital and their expenses. Moreover, Key Informant number 10 states that *"Paikot ikot lang ang puhunan"* (Rolling the earnings). SMEs are prone to closure of business because of having small capital to continue their business. SMEs use their daily earnings to buy materials to create a new product to use in selling to attract more customers to buy their products. Rolling their income is often used by SMEs to continue their business at able to sustain their daily needs.

Based on the answers of participants they lack in capital to support their business and meet the needs of their customers. According to Housing News Desk (2022), capital allows the business to buy the materials that they need in their production. Moreover, capital helps grow the business by improving its production and quality. Faster Capital (2023) viewed that capital is the lifeblood of a business, if they do not have this there will be a problem. It is used to support every need of a business in its day-to-day transactions. The second category of challenges experienced by the SMEs is management. Management is a different type of living, there should be a precise decision with accurate results because if you fail it will have a big impact on your business. Moreover, having managing skills is important today because it has a huge impact on the future of a business.

Strategies is the second theme and is a set of plans that business owners perform to achieve their goals. Businesses today are expected to do extra time to get more sales and be known in their respective fields. In today's world businesses in a certain have the same identity or they have the same product or services to offer to their customers. However, in terms of selling their products, they must have a unique way of selling so that they will be able to connect to their target customers. Based on the responses of SMEs they have their way of how to work with their production.

Key Informant number 2 shares *“Pokusan lang po namin, lahat naman po nagagwan ng paraan”* (Let us just focus, everything has been done in a way). Most of the small businesses' problems today are how they handle their business. Some of them often close their business in their early stage because of mismanagement. As the Key Informant states above, it is good if they make solutions for every problem because in business there are always issues and the owner should think about what may come in the future. The Key Informant number 6 is *“Matagal na sya pero di pa nakaregister sa DTI”* (Long-standing business but not yet registered with DTI). One of the reasons why businesses today are prone to closure is because they are not registered and properly informed about the important matters in a business. They make decisions wherein they put themselves in the wrong way instead of getting the good benefits ahead. If a business is registered and has knowledge in regards to policies and how to grow their business they might become successful. Moreover, Key Informant number 7 says *“Empleyado din ako sa sarili ko”* (I am one of the workers also). Most of the small businesses today are run by their owner only and have no one by their side to help them. The owner is the cook, cashier, and other positions in a business. If only they knew the proper handling of business, they may create a solution to problems that may arise. Likewise, Key Informant number 8 states *“Wala pa kaming masyadong alam”* (We do not know much yet). Most of the newcomer in the business world do not have enough idea in the proper handling of their business. It is preferred to attend seminars provided by the Department of Trade and Industries so as new in the field you will be able to manage your business. This training could be your key to more customers, better earnings, and to the success of your business. Lastly, Key Informant number 9 says *“Nung una wala naman kaming alam kung papano”* (At first, we did not know how). Like the statements of the previous informants, this informant does not know how to manage her business. But along the way, with the help of the training given by the government, they can adapt to the situation of today's

business world. All of the starters in business, come with nothing but as they experience something in their day-to-day transaction it serves as a lesson for them to keep up and face the reality.

Based on the responses of SMEs some of them have their way on how to run their businesses, but others stated that they do not know exactly how to manage their businesses. The study by Das (2023) states that over 90 percent of newly installed businesses today break down because of a lack of management skills. Management is the center of all transactions in a business. Before it was easy for us to sell products and earn money because there were only a few competitors and not so new marketing strategy. These days it is hard for us to sell because of the competition in the market internal and external. We can always say that if there is good management a business will earn money and can be known in their field.

Moreover, Cirillo et al. (2023) added that having academic training that focuses on managerial skills is key to the success of a company. The owner should know how to manage his business because there are many competitors in the field.

The table in this area contains the significant statements of the small and medium entrepreneurs (SMEs) before they undergo SME Roving Academy.

Table 1
Theme of the Lived Experiences of the Key Informants
in terms of their Personal Lives

Key Informants	Responses	Code	Theme
1.	<i>“May maisave lang ako sa gasul sa lending parang rolling ko lang”</i> (I can only save something for gasul and lending like I'm just rolling)	Production	Capital
3	<i>“Ako kasi by order lang”</i> (I'm just by order)		
4	<i>“Yung kita ibibili”</i> (The income will use to bought)		
5	<i>“Pag may puhunan lang ako makakatinda”</i> (I can only sell if I have the capital)		
10	<i>“Paikot ikot lang ang puhunan”</i> (Rolling the earnings)		
2	<i>“Pokusan lang po namin, lahat naman po nagagwan ng paraan”</i> (Let us just focus, everything has been done in a way)	Management	Strategies
6	<i>“Matagal na sya pero di pa nakaregister sa DTI”</i> (Long-standing business but not yet registered with DTI)		

- 7 *“Empleyado din ako sa sarili ko”* (I am one of the workers also)
 - 8 *“Wala pa kaming masyadong alam”* (We do not know much yet)
 - 9 *“Nung una wala naman kaming alam kung papano”* (At first we did not know how)
-

Social Aspects. The analysis on the data generated one category of the challenges of SMEs on their social aspects before undergoing the training. That is selling, under the category are the specific challenges experienced by the SMEs.

This category experienced by the SMEs is selling. Selling products is not that easy, there are times that a business does not have sales or they have a very low sale. A business should open for a different marketing strategy, adapting new way of selling products could be a good help to the business. But it depends also on the budget if it can sustain that kind of technique. The theme under selling, as business owner we need to be more vigilant in terms of our market, new marketing strategies are showing because of the needs of the customers. In some businesses they are adapting to what is the trend in the social. Marketing strategies in one of the important things that businesses should have to survive in this changing world. Some of the respondents shared their thoughts regarding marketing strategy.

The Key Informant number 1 says *“Affordable lang at masarap lang po”* (Affordable and delicious). In selling your products, especially in a place where there are competitors you need to create something much better than their products. To sell is one of the most crucial parts in business your need to be more creative yet your products need to cover the needs of your customer to satisfy them. Likewise, Key Informant number 2 states *“Promo po kami sa presyo, pero inaano rin po naming ang quality”* (We lower our price, but we are also promoting the quality).

It is important that a business owner have to be more creative in selling their products, they can add something to make it more eye catching or something new and different. Earning money is not easy, yes there are people who earn more in selling their products because of the demand but due to the bulk orders they receive the quality is compromised. Moreover, Key Informant number 3 says *“Nabigay akong sample, pag may mga bago akong product napatikim muna ako bago napa order”* (I give a sample, if I have a new product, I let them taste it first before I get the order). In selling your product you need to set its quality; do not think of the money you will receive at the of the day. Other than the quality your need to make you own marketing strategy on how sell your product. Some of the businesses often fail to continue their business because of low sales. Their marketing skills needs to be upgrade and think of possible option to catch the attention of customers.

The Key Informant number 4 added *“Naglalako lang ako tapos ang mga anak ko sa mga kakilala nila”* (I sell in the street and my children with their acquaintances). It signifies

marketing strategy in selling their products to get sales. Selling on the streets is one of the known strategies, small businesses use this style of selling to get customers because nowadays there are a lot of sellers same of your product. In addition, Key Informant number 5 says *“Naglalako-lako lang ako”* (I sell only in the street) and Key informant number 6 *“Puro pa-free taste lang ang mother ko halos siguro kalahati ng products naming nauubos sa free taste”* (My mother only uses free taste, maybe half of our products are used up in free taste). Having the right skills in selling your products can be mean a lot to your business. Both Key Informants shows strategy on selling their products, most of the time sellers are onto the newest or trending items today. But there are a lot of sellers of the same product to compete with, so a set of marketing styles needs to make to get customers.

Moreover, Key Informant number 7 *“Meron ako sa facebook account nagtatanggap ako minsan nag titinda ako sa street”* (I have facebook account where I take orders, sometimes I sell in the street). One of the newest marketing strategies nowadays is the use of social media in selling products. Selling products in street can be upgraded using Facebook one of the social media markets today. While you are in the street you can post your products online and there are a lot of people that may see. Using new technology in selling products is the most possible way to get the attention of your target market and attract new customers. Key Informant number 8 added, *“Online padin kaya lang di ganon kadali mag target”* (We well online but its not that easy to target customers). Using new technology in selling products said to be the easiest way to target your market. Yes, but it is not like you are going to post and get new customer. They need to be more creative, make some tag line that will catch the attention of your target market.

In addition, Key Informant number 9 says *“Binabagsak sa mga pasalubong stores”* (Dropped in pasalubong stores). Having more connection can give more clients and sales. Attending different seminars for small businesses sponsored by the government can give more connections. These connections may lead the owner to get their target market and make more sales. Lastly, Key Informant number 10 says *“Nakadisplay lang sa labas, minsan napost sa GC”* (Just displayed outside, sometimes posted on GC). Using both traditional and new way of selling can be more helpful to the business. These kinds of strategies may capture the attention of people looking for something.

As stated above based on their responses, some of the respondents have their own version on how they market their products and services. Most of them adapted the use of social media platform as their additional style of earning money. They use this kind of strategy because of the pandemic before. Some of them did not know and shy to use the social media and making their own style on how they are going to make money.

According to the study of Hansika (2022) marketing are sets of steps used by several companies to promote and be known in their field to earn money. Aside from management, marketing is among of the most critical parts of a business today. Its main objective to gain awareness in the market to gain new customers and sells the products or services to them.

In addition, in the study of Mbatha et al. (2023) stated that people are using both digital and face-to-face marketing strategies, however it is advisable that they need to study and adopt advance knowledge about the online marketing that will give them competitive advantage from the competitors. In this time of innovation there are new strategies that came up because of the level of the needs of people. The owner may adopt new techniques to increase their sales.

The table in this area contains the significant statements of the small medium entrepreneurs (SMEs) before they undergo SME Roving Academy.

Table 2
Theme of the Lived Experiences of the Key Informants
in terms of their Social Aspects

Key Informants	Responses	Code	Theme
1	<i>“Affordable lang at masarap lang po”</i> (Affordable and delicious)		
2	<i>” Promo po kami sa presyo, pero inaano rin po naming ang quality”</i> (We lower our price, but we are also promoting the quality)		
3	<i>“Nabigay akong sample, pag may mga bago akong product napatikim muna ako bago napa order”</i> (I give a sample, if I have a new product, I let them taste it first before I get the order)		
4	<i>”Naglalako lang ako tapos ang mga anak ko sa mga kakilala nila”</i> (I sell in the street and my children with their acquaintances)		
5	<i>“Naglalako-lako lang ako”</i> (I sell only in the street)	Selling	Marketing Strategies
6	<i>“Puro pa-free taste lang ang mother ko halos siguro kalahati ng products naming nauubos sa free taste”</i> (My mother only uses free taste; maybe half of our products are used up in free taste)		
7	<i>“Meron ako sa facebook account nagtatanggap ako minsan sa nag titinda ako sa street”</i> (I have facebook account where I take orders, sometimes I sell in the street)		
8	<i>“Online padin kaya lang di ganon kadali mag target”</i> (We do well online but it is not that easy to target customers)		

- 9 “*Binabagsak sa mga pasalubong stores*”
(Dropped in pasalubong stores)
 - 10 “*Nakadisplay lang sa labas, minsan napost sa GC*” (Just displayed outside, sometimes posted on GC)
-

Economic Circumstances. The analysis on the data generated two categories of the challenges of SMEs on their economic circumstances before undergoing the training. That is reordering and standard of living, under the category are the specific challenges experienced by the SMEs.

The first category experienced by the SMEs is reordering. Reordering products is a good sign of good products and services from your business. It only means that your business is doing well and little by little getting more customers. The theme under reordering is satisfaction it is the term that we use in determining the quality of the products and production. Satisfaction from the customer is the business needs to attain in order for them to retain their client. If they satisfy them, then they will earn more sales. Customers will always come back to a business to order not only because they like the product or service, one of the reasons is being comfortable in the area. Satisfying customers really makes the business successful. The participants shared their thoughts regarding the customers satisfaction.

Key Informant number 1 says “*Oo naman nasasatisfy ko naman sila*” (Of course they are satisfied). By satisfying your customers may lead in having a good sale and build reputation. With the increase in prices of all the materials we need, there are business that still making the same product they sell from the start. The quality of the product is the most important in the customers, even a business increased the price of their product they will still avail it. In addition, Key Informants number 3 states “*Oo kasi naulit sila eh, bumibili ulit sila*” (Yes, because they repeat and order again) and Key Informant number 5 “*Oo man, may nag ooro-order man*” (Yes, they are ordering).

The customer will keep on patronizing the product if it is quality still the same. The price of a product is nothing to customers if they are satisfied. The quality of the product will build the composition in the field and hold customers.

As stated above based on their responses, some of the respondents have satisfied their customers and make them to order again their products. On the study of Lee et al. (2016) states that it is hard for a business to know what their customers wants and needs, but if they met those things, it could be a way of profitability. In the study of Haaften (2023) customer satisfaction has positive effect on the business profitability and it forms the foundation of the success of the business.

The second category experienced by the SMES is standard of living. This term pertains to level of satisfaction a certain people that changes the way they act in several ways in life. Most of the successful business have a great impact the life of the owner, being satisfied by getting what they want also means that our economy is growing.

This is the theme under standard of living, income pertains to the amount that a certain person or business receives after they do their job. Not all businesses are getting more income, some of them receives low to no sales in a day. Income can give the owner what he needs for himself and for his family. If the business has great way of selling their products and be able to connect to their customers, then the business will have more sales. Some of the participants shared their thoughts regarding their income.

Key Informant number 2 says, *“Nakukukha narin po naming yung mga needs naming sap ag araw-araw”* (We get what we need every day) and Key Informant number 4 *“Oo basta makakuha lang ng pang ano sa mga bata”* (Yes just to get something for my kids).

The main reason of doing business is to earn money and to support the needs of their family. It is important that they have the skills mentioned above to obtain good sales. There is no problem if a business has good sales, to obtain that the owner needs to be more focused on the things he wants to do and apply all his experiences.

Moreover, Key informant number 6 states *“Hindi naman kasi gnun lagi may kumikita”* (Not all the time we earn money), and Key Informant number 7 *“Hindi sya regular kung baga sa kabote pasulpot sulpot lang”* (It is not regular all the time), and Key Informant number 8 *“Dati parin sir, di pa naman ganun kalaki ang kinikita”* (In the past, sir, the income was not that big). Not all businesses earn more sales, some of them get the return only capital. It is hard to compete in this new modern day of business because of new strategies like using social media plat forms. It is important that the owners do not stop running their business, they keep on striving hard to get what they wanted. In addition, Key Informant number 9 says *“Dati lang”* (Same as before) and Key Informant number 10 states *“Simple lang sir, maano lang yung mga pangangailngan ng pamilya ko”* (It is simple sir, just the needs of my family). Some of the successful businesses despite earning more sales and getting more of what they want they remain the same. They are living the life of what they are before, they are happy on their situation now and they keep on developing their products to excel in the field. Sometimes living the same of what they are before and enjoying the life they have now could be the most precious moment in their life.

In their responses stated above, participants allocate their income just for the needs of their family and they were happy of that. Some of them were not earning the same amount of their capital they will be having in a day. On the study of Kronenberg (2011) states that a simple living is a way of choice to get a much more comparative result of their doing. Any person who has been practicing simple living is happy even they are only using small amount of their resources they are still grateful while earning money.

The table in this area contains the significant statements of the small medium entrepreneurs (SMEs) before they undergo SME Roving Academy.

Table 3
Theme of the Lived Experiences of the Key Informants
in terms of their Economic Aspects

Key Informants	Responses	Code	Theme
1.	“Oo naman nasasatisfy ko naman sila” (Of course they are satisfied)		
3	“Oo kasi naulit sila eh, bumibili ulit sila” (Yes, because they repeat and order again)	Reordering	Satisfaction
5	“Oo man may nag ooro-order man” (Yes, they are ordering)		
2	“Nakukukha narin po naming yung mga needs naming sap ag araw-araw” (We get what we need every day)		
4	“Oo basta makakuha lang ng pang ano sa mga bata” (Yes just to get something for my kids)		
6	“Hindi naman kasi gnun lagi may kumikita” (Not all the time we earn money)		
7	“Hindi sya regular kung baga sa kabote pasulpot sulpot lang” (In the past, sir, the income was not that big)	Standard of Living	Income
8	“Dati parin sir, di pa naman ganun kalaki ang kinikita”		
9	“Dati lang” (Same like before)		
10	“Simple lang sir, maano lang yung mga pangangailangan ng pamilya ko” (It is simple sir, just the needs of my family)		

Challenges Faced by the Program’s Beneficiaries upon its Introduction Encompassing Aspects.

Personal Lives. The analysis on the data generated one category of the challenges of SMEs on their economic circumstances before undergoing the training. That is understanding, under the category are the specific challenges experienced by the SMEs.

The first category experienced by the SMEs is understanding. Understanding is the ability to comprehend something which are vital in every action that we do. For a business owner if there is a problem, he needs first to know what is the reason behind before taking any actions. The theme corresponding to understanding is the implementation of all the learnings that you have learned. In the implementation the owner needs to ensure that he understand all the things.

With regards to this, all of the target participants of this study shared their thoughts. Key Informant number 1 says, *“Napapagod lang pero tuloy padin”* (Tired but still going). In running a business is tiring, its like they are running an organization because of the things they need to accomplish to have a good result. In business sometimes they win or lost, they just need to focus to their goals and make some new way to improve it. The competition is there, but they need to adapt and be strong to face the reality of changes. Key informant number 2 states, *“Maayos naman po naipaliwanag”* (Well explained), and Key Informant number 3 *“hindi naman, kompleto talaga ang DTI pag may patraining”* (No, DTI is really complete when there is training), and Key Informant number 4 says *“Okay yung speaker kaya ako first time mag attends kulang yung mga kaalaman ko sa training”* (The speaker is ok, but it was my first and I do not have knowledge in training), and Key Informant number 5 *“Minsan parang hindi ko naiintindihan yung iba”* (Sometimes I do not understand others) and Key Informant number 6 added, *“Para sakin kasi laging try my best kung kaya ko gagawin ko”* (For me, I always try my best) and Key Informant number 7 *“Ay oo naman kaya naman”* (Of course, I can).

It is normal for a newcomer the things they do not know and cannot do. The trainings given by the Department of Trade and Industries is set to catch all the needs of small SMEs in running their business. They have their expert to share information to the trainees, they will provide the right information that they need and guide them.

On the other hand, Key Informant number 8 says, *“Hindi naman po kasi bukod sa training may internet naman po pwede tayo mag explore”* (Not at all, apart from the training there is internet so we can explore) and Key Informant number 9 states, *“Kung applicable naman sa business namin yung training tingin ko maapply namin”* (If the training is applicable to our business, I think we can apply it). The government set to have training for the small business to help them grow in their respective field, it is based on the needs of a business that needs to be fix. If they are still in doubt, we have the technology to use in searching the possible way to fix a problem or to get tips to from various businessman. There are several ways to improve the business, they just need to be more adaptable in all the things. However, Key Informant number 10 states, *“Ang problema talaga po naming oras, kaya di naming napagtutuunan ng pansin”* (The real problem is our time, that is why we do not pay attention). The trainings are there and all the support assistance from the government to prevent the business to closure. However, there are circumstances that the owner did not put all his efforts in accomplishing his goals. The owner needs to separate his own personal life and have a balance environment. If they want to succeed in the field focus on the goals and earn the things they deserve. Hard work always gives something in return, in the business it ensure the achievement of goals.

In a business, the owner should always be open minded in everything that can be helpful to the business. It is important that the trainer explains well all his topics so that their clients in the said event could easily get their objectives. Not all the clients could understand them because of their educational status. But even though that is their situation they are eager to learn more about business. Base on the result of interview stated above their responses it says that most of them have understand their training. It

is very important that a person understand the information so that he can deliver well and should have their materials in order for them to perform well also. Moreover, a person should have confidence in doing their job. On the study of Somwethee et al. (2023), stated that it is important that an owner should have the entrepreneurial capability to achieve their goals.

The table in this area contains the significant statements of the small medium entrepreneurs (SMEs) during their training for SME Roving Academy.

Table 4
Theme of the Challenges Encountered by the SMEs along their Personal Lives

Key Informants	Responses	Code	Theme
1.	<i>“Napapagod lang pero tuloy padin”</i> (Tired but still going)		
2	<i>“Maayos naman po naipaliwanag”</i> (Well explained)		
3	<i>“hindi naman, kompleto talaga ang DTI pag may patraining”</i> (No, DTI is really complete when there is training)		
4	<i>“Okay yung speaker kaya ako first time mag attends kulang yung mga kaalaman ko sa training”</i> (The speaker is ok, but it was my first and I do not have knowledge in training)		
5	<i>“Minsan parang hindi ko naiintindihan yung iba”</i> (Sometimes I do not understand others)		
6	<i>“Para sakin kasi laging gtry my best kung kaya ko gagawin ko”</i> (For me, I always try my best)	Understanding	Implementation
7	<i>“Ay oo naman kaya naman”</i> (Of course, I can)		
8	<i>“Hindi naman po kasi bukod sa training may internet naman po pwede tayo mag explore”</i> (Hindi naman po, apart from the training there is internet so we can explore)		
9	<i>“Kung applicable naman sa business naming yung training tingin ko maapply naming”</i> (If the training is applicable to our business, I think we can apply it)		
10	<i>“Ang problema talaga po naming oras, kaya di naming napagtutuunan ng pansin”</i> (The real problem is our time, that is why we do not pay attention)		

Their capabilities can contribute to their performance and help them in acquiring new customers to earn more money. On the other hand, in the study of Ellitan (2021) state that if a business increases the use of information technology it will likely increase its business performance. In their training, it is important that the lead agency can explain all details in their training program so that the entrepreneur can perform well in their field.

Social Aspects. The analysis on the data generated one category of the challenges of SMEs on their economic circumstances before undergoing the training. That is connection, under the category are the specific challenges experienced by the SMEs.

The first category experienced by the SMEs is connection. Connection is pertaining to the relation that we have with people that surrounds us. The theme under the said category above is connection, it pertains to the bond that they have with the people that surrounds them. As a business owner they need to build a good relation to their customers so that they come back again and become a loyal customer. Having a good relation to the customers gives positive effect in the business. With regards to this, all the target participants of this study shared their thoughts.

Key Informant number 1 says, *“Oo kaya naman, nagkakasabay lang pag labasan”* (Yes, they are just going out together) and Key Informant number 2 *“Yung pagkakaran naming ng quality sa serbisyo namin sakanila”* (The fact that we have quality in our service to them), Key Informant number 4 also says, *“Don lang kami sa quality of product at binabalik-balik kami”* (We only care about the quality of the product and they still coming to us) and Key Informant number 5 states, *“Si customers baga dapat unawain mo”* (Customer first). Having connection to customer is a good sign that the business is doing good. People who continue to support the product reflects how good the product is. Putting all the effort to give what customer deserves could lead to good relationship. On the other hand, Key Informant number 3 states, *“Ano ngayon online ang inaano ng DTI, sabi nila pano ang mga lola”* (DTI are teaching online, other people says that we are old for that). Online selling is the new trend in selling all kinds of products. This kind of strategy use since the beginning of pandemic to lessen the physical contact with other people. The government gives training regarding the use of several online plat forms to ease the selling of products. Their trainings are for all people of all ages, sex, and the likes. Moreover, regarding the use of technology Key Informant number 6 says, *“Mas grabe ngayon ang online platform”* (The online platform is worse now) and Key Informant number 7 *“Nagkukuha ako ng mga ideya saknila rin”* (I get idea from them too). Almost all businesses today using social media plat form to market their products and services. However, social media plat form uses by several people to take down their competitors by spreading false news. In addition, not all social media of businesses are harmful, some of them share their tips on how they become successful in business.

In addition, Key Informant number 8 says, *“Naimprove po relations naming sa mga customers at dagdag kaalaman”* (We have improved relations with customers and added knowledge), and Key Informant number 9 states *“Oo nakatulong sa productivity namin”* (Yes, it helped our productivity), and Key Informant number 10 *“Feeling ko sir oo,*

nakatulong po sya” (I feel sir yes, it helped.). These informants revealed that using technology really helps them in terms of productivity.

Social media platforms improved the marketing strategy of a business and create more customers. Also, using machine as part of new technology in business, allows them to lessen the burden on them in terms of using time, money, and effort. In managing a business, it is very important that the owner or manager should have skills and their connections in selling are one of the most important ingredients in running a business. Selling own product using own style is good but as a newcomer in the field they should have connections to have a chance to grow. There are several types of marketing strategies that some of the businesses today are using. Using social media platform is the most well-known marketing strategy and it is very helpful to the business.

Base on the result of their responses all of them have their own style of marketing but some do not know how to use social media platform because of their age, and they do not have the courage to show themselves online. But during their training they taught on how to use it well so that they can easily attract new customers and gain sales and build their relationship with their customers. It is very important that they adapt in the changes in marketing because it can help them in achieving goals.

The table in this area contains the significant statements of the small medium entrepreneurs (SMEs) during their training for SME Roving Academy.

Table 5
Theme of the Challenges Encountered by the SMEs along their Social Aspects

Key Informants	Responses	Code	Theme
1.	<i>“Oo kaya naman, nagkakasabay lang pag labasan”</i> (Yes, they are just going out together)		
2	<i>“Yung pagkakaran naming ng quality sa serbisyo namin sakanila”</i> (The fact that we have quality in our service to them)		
3	Ano ngayon online ang inaano ng DTI, sabi nila pano ang mga lola		
4	<i>“Don lang kami sa quality of product at binabalik-balik kami”</i> (We only care about the quality of the product and they still coming to us)	Conne ction	Relation
5	<i>“Si customers бага dapat unawain mo”</i> (Customer first)		
6	<i>“Mas grabe ngayon ang online platform”</i> (The online platform is worse now)		
7	<i>“Nagkukuha ako ng mga ideya saknila rin”</i> (I get idea from them too)		

- 8 *“Naimprove po relations naming sa mga customers at dagdag kaalaman”* (We have improved relations with customers and added knowledge)
 - 9 *“Oo nakatulong sa productivity namin”* (Yes, it helped our productivity)
 - 10 *“Feeling ko sir oo, nakatulong po sya”* (I feel sir yes, it helped.)
-

According to the of Adams (2023) state that a good relationship to the customer is the key to your success. Building the trust and creating connections to customers gives them the security that may lead to a more customers and sales. In this time of new era of business online transaction is the new trend, most of the people now are buying their goods online because it is less hustle for them. Moreover, in the study of Sa’adah et al. (2023) state that a good corporate image and marketing has a big impact in their customer loyalty. Having those capabilities can help a business to gain connections and increase their productivity and sales.

Economic Circumstances. The analysis on the data generated one category of the challenges of SMEs on their economic circumstances before undergoing the training. That is production, under the category are the specific challenges experienced by the SMEs. Production is the process of combining materials or ingredients to produce something that suits the needs of the people. If there is good production there will be more sales for a business, focusing on the production could generate positive effects.

The theme under the category production is the selling. Selling pertains to a transaction in exchange of money. With regards to this, all the target participants of this study shared their thoughts. Key Informant number 1 state, *“Oo kaya naman lalo kapag rush hour”* (Yes, especially during rush hour) about their production, also Key Informant number 2 *“Toka toka po kami, first come first serve”* (We have our job divided and first come first serve), Key Informant number 4 *“Tulong tulong kaming mga anak ko”* (We help each other) and Key Informant number 5 *“Kaya naman katulong ang anak ko”* (Yes, with the help of my children), and Key Informant number 10 *“Pag madaming order, tulong kaming dalawa”* (When there are many orders, we both help). In running a business there is a need of having somebody to help do the things. Most of the time a small business helps by their own relatives in producing their products. They are the most trusted by the owner and easy to monitor. There are times that a business receives a bulk order that needs to deliver on time. Camaraderie in accomplishing things could really help your business to attain its goals. Key Informant number 3 says, *“Maraming naitulong sa aming produksyon at sales”* (It helped us a lot in our production and sales) and Key Informant number 6 *“Nag repeat order na sila”* (They have already made a repeat order). The trainings in business are very important for the newcomer, it will serve as basis and allows them to make a wise decision. As newcomer in the business, they need to focus on what he wants to do, they could face several problems along the way. If they are making the right decision, then their business is going to have more clients and sales. Their goals are achieved. However, Key Informant number 7 says, *“Yun nga minsan mahirap ang kahoy para mkagawa”* (Sometimes we cannot find wood).

Key Informant number 8 *“Pag may bagon order tinitingnan ko muna ang stocks naming”* (When there is an order, I check our stocks first). In selling products there is a need to always check the stocks before accommodating some orders. Maybe because of the hectic schedule in production, the owner forgets of the inventories. Sometimes, even if they know their work process, there is no supply of materials in the area. That is why they need to have a futuristic mind, always think of possible things that could happen, and focus on their goals. On the other hand, Key informant number 9 says, *“Pag sa gabi ako nagchecheck ng orders online then by morning papasa ko sa production”* (When I check orders online at night then by morning, I pass them to production). As mentioned above about the inventories of materials, if they can produce then the section handling this will pass it to their production. There should be a balance so that the production team will not feel worried about where to get materials at the time of their production.

In a business we can determine its earning base on its production, it plays vital role in an organization. Production in the process of transforming raw materials into an item which the customer will buy and consume or use. In production there several steps that need to be taken to achieve the quality of the product to satisfy the clients. There are things needed in every production such as raw materials and capital to purchase the materials.

Based on the interpretation of the responses above, most of them have the capacity to produce or continue their production. All of them have given the material kits from the DTI to ensure their production are all set and safe. But some of them stops their production due to the lack of capital to purchase items or lacking other materials needed. On the study of Pearson (2021) stated that production is the most important in the business, without this activity there is no production of goods that people need. Production has several steps that raw materials go through, and it should be precise every weight of materials to have a same size and amount per item. In a production, an owner should have enough money to purchase all the needed materials.

The table in this area contains the significant statements of the small medium entrepreneurs (SMEs) during their training for SME Roving Academy.

Table 6
Theme of the Challenges Encountered by the
SMEs along their Economic Aspects

Key Informants	Responses	Code	Theme
1.	<i>“Oo kaya naman lalo kapag rush hour”</i> (Yes, especially during rush hour)		
2	<i>“Toka toka po kami, first come first serve”</i> (We have our job divided and first come first serve)		
3	<i>“Maraming naitulong sa aming produksyon at sales”</i> (It helped us a lot in our production and sales)		
4	<i>“Tulong tulong kaming mga anak ko”</i> (We help each other)		
5	<i>“Kaya naman katulong ang anak ko”</i> (Yes, with the help of my children)		
6	<i>“Nag repeat order na sila”</i> (They have already made a repeat order)	Production	Selling
7	<i>“Yun nga minsan mahirap ang kahoy para mkagawa”</i> (Sometimes we cannot find wood)		
8	<i>“Pag may bagon order tinitingnan ko muna ang stocks naming”</i> (When there is an order, I check our stocks first)		
9	<i>“Pag sa gabi ako nagchecheck ng orders online then by morning papasa ko sa production”</i> (When I check orders online at night then by morning, I pass them to production)		
10	<i>“Pag madaming order, tulong kaming dalawa”</i> (When there are many orders, we both help)		

Changes in the Lives of Program Beneficiaries of DTI SME Roving Academy

Personal Lives. The analysis on the data generated one category of the challenges of SMEs on their economic circumstances before undergoing the training. That is decision making, under the category are the specific challenges experienced by the SMEs. Decision making is the process of applying all the learnings that a person learned or experience. It is important to have a good decision making to ensure its result.

The theme under the category production is the skills. Skills pertains to the ability of a person to perform well using his idea or information. Skills help the business in production and selling and having skills could lead a business to the top of the line. With regards to this, all of the target participants of this study shared their thoughts. The Key Informant number 1 says, *“Napataas talaga nito ang aming skills”* (It really increased our skills), Key Informant number 2 *“Opo, talagang tumaas ang aming benta”* (Yes, our sales have really

increased), Key Informant number 3 *“Nakatulong sila samin sa pagmamanahe at pag handle ng business”* (They helped us in managing and handling the business), Key Informant number 4 *“Nakatulong sa kung paano naming ihandle ang business”* (Helped with how we handle business), and Key Informant number 5 *“Naayos ang aking pag manage lalo na sa budgeting”* (My management has been fixed, especially in budgeting). Training really helps businesses to survive their daily transactions.

Those trainings given by the government is based on their assessment on the submitted information by the small businesses in a certain area. They choose the right person or expert to explain and allows them to learn and change their situation from nothing to a well-known businessman. Managing a business small or big is hard, the owner should be well equipped by different kind of skills. Because in this new world of business there are so many issues or problems that they need to face.

Moreover, Key Informant number 6 says, *“Naging maayos ang managerial skills ko”* (My managerial skills have improved), Key Informant number 7 *“Oo, nakuha naming yung goals at natuto ng managerial skills”* (Yes, we got the goals and learned managerial skills), Key Informant number 8 *“Maayos ko ng nahahandle ang bawat issues”* (I can handle every issue well), Key Informant number 9 *“Nakakatulong na sya sa lahat, sa purchasing, production”* (It helped us in purchasing, production), and Key Informant number 10 *“Mas nagagawaa ko na ng paraan ang bawat problema”* (I can find a way to every problem). The trainings given by the government could really uplift their managerial skills, this may lead them in achieving their goals. Also, their purchasing skills will improve resulting to a better production and sales. Lastly, by the help of the trainings it can create their own way of handling problems.

Training could of be beneficial in all the people, but it depends on the person whom to apply their learnings in their life. Training varied based on their needs. The Department of Trade and Industry allotted their time and effort to help those small businesses in pursuing their goals. The learnings from them can be use in managing properly their business and to earn more sales.

As interpreted above the responses, all of them have a good response pertaining to the training they have attended, and it help them to get some of their goals. They can now easily manage some issues in business, make wise decisions that produces good results, and they live on their own without the help of other.

According to the study by Yimam (2022), training has a significant impact on the performance of employees. It sharpens their skills, knowledge and motivates them to be productive. It is a continuous process, and the trainings are based on the needs of a client.

The table in this area contains the significant statements of the small medium entrepreneurs (SMEs) after their training for SME Roving Academy.

Table 7
Theme of the Changes in the Lives of the Key Informants
along their Personal Lives

Key Informants	Responses	Code	Theme
1.	<i>“Napataas talaga nito ang aming skills”</i> (It really increased our skills)		
2	<i>“Opo, talagang tumaas an aming benta”</i> (Yes, our sales have really increased) Opo, talagang tumaas an aming benta		
3	<i>“Nakatulong sa kung paano naming ihandle ang business”</i> (Helped with how we handle business)		
4	<i>“Nakatulong sa kung paano naming ihandle ang business”</i> (Helped with how we handle business)		
5	<i>“Naayos ang aking pag manage lalo na sa budgeting”</i> (My management has been fixed, especially in budgeting)	Decision Making	Skills
6	<i>“Naging maayos ang managerial skills ko”</i> (My managerial skills have improved)		
7	<i>“Oo, nakuha naming yung goals at natuto ng managerial skills”</i> (Yes, we got the goals and learned managerial skills)		
8	<i>“Maayos ko ng nahahandle ang bawat issues”</i> (I can handle every issue well)		
9	<i>“Nakakatulong na sya sa lahat, sa purchasing, production”</i> (It helped us in purchasing, production)		
10	<i>“Mas nagagawaa ko na ng paraan ang bawat problema”</i> (I can find a way to every problem)		

Social Aspect. The analysis on the data generated one category of the challenges of SMEs on their economic circumstances before undergoing the training. That is customers, under the category are the specific challenges experienced by the SMEs. It is pertaining to a person or group of people who buys your product or services. They are the most important part of a business transaction. Customers rely on the product because it is their need, that is why the business owner should know first their needs before.

The theme under the category production is the socialization. Socialization pertains to the ability of a person to connect with people. Being connected to the people is important because they bring success. The more customers the business have the more sales that the business will have. With regards to this, all the target participants of this study shared their thoughts. Key Informant number 1 says, *“Oo tumaas talaga”* (Yes, it really

increased), Key Informant number 2 *“Yes po malaking tulong talaga po”* (Yes, it is really a big help), Key Informant number 3 *“Oo tumaas talaga customers namin”* (Yes, our customers have really increased), Key Informant number 4 *“Oo naman kahit papano pero my dati na akong parabili”* (Yes a little, but I already have customers before), and Key Informant number 5 *“Oo meron naman bagong customers”* (Yes, there are lot of customers). In the place of training proper there are a lot of business owner that a businessman could meet. There is a possibility that they become a partner of your owned business. Meeting with the other business owners could be beneficial on both sides because of the shared learnings and tips based on their experiences. Socializing really builds a connection between the owner and customers. Moreover, Key Informant number 6 says, *“Mas nakilala na ang aming produkto”* (Our product has become better known), Key Informant number 7 *“Oo may mga nakilala akong business owner”* (Yes, I met some business owners), Key Informant number 8 *“Nag karoon kami ng bagong customers”* (We have new customers), Key Informant number 9 *“Nadag dagan din ang customers namin”* (Our customers also increased), and Key Informant number 10 *“Opo nadagdagan po ang customers namin”* (Yes, our customers have increased).

Socialization is very important for a business owner; they need to go to the other places to meet people with same products but with a lot of experiences. That information, the experiences of will help your business to make connection. Socialization is one of the topics on the training given by the government to enhance the marketing skills of the business owners and generate more sales. The connection they made will help boost marketing, showcases products, create more customers and earn more sales.

In putting up a business the owner needs to assess first the product or services has a market. The market is the customers, they are the one to buy or grab your services. In this new era of business, customers are the most important they can increase the growth and success by patronizing products or services. Social media platforms are the most effective way today to gain more clients and earn money.

As stated above according to the responses of ten (10) small entrepreneurs they already have their customers before they attended training in DTI. After the training it really helps them to attract new customers, be known to their respective field and earn more sales. Socialization or building relationship to the customers is really an important ingredient to the success of a business. Also, a good quality products or services has big impact to the clients' s satisfaction that makes them buy the products or services again. Social media platform is the most effective way to gather more clients for the business. There are so many ways on how to use social media platform.

The table in this area contains the significant statements of the small medium entrepreneurs (SMEs) after their training for SME Roving Academy.

Table 8
Theme of the Changes in the Lives of the Key Informants
along their Social Aspects

Key Informants	Responses	Code	Theme
1.	<i>“Oo tumaas talaga”</i> (Yes, it really increased)		
2	<i>“Yes po malaking tulong talaga po”</i> (Yes, it is really a big help)		
3	<i>“Oo tumaas talaga customers namin”</i> (Yes, our customers have really increased)		
4	<i>“Oo naman kahit papano pero my dati na akong parabili”</i> (Yes a little, but I already have customers before)		
5	<i>“Oo meron naman bagong customers”</i> (Yes, there are lot of customers)	Customers	Socialization
6	<i>“Mas nakilala na ang aming produkto”</i> (Our product has become better known)		
7	<i>“Oo may mga nakilala akong business owner”</i> (Yes, I met some business owners)		
8	<i>“Nag karoon kami ng bagong customers”</i> (We have new customers)		
9	<i>“Nadag dagan din ang customers namin”</i> (Our customers also increased)		
10	<i>“Opo nadagdagan po ang customers namin”</i> (Yes, our customers have increased)		

In the study of Bruce et al. (2022) state that social media is very important to company and created more customers to gain more sales. The customers have a very wide range of information regarding to his needs and they are searching for the right information they need. The social media has become popular since pandemic, but it created rooms to lessen the effort of people.

Economic Circumstances. The analysis on the data generated one category of the challenges of SMEs in their economic circumstances before undergoing the training. That is financial, under the category are the specific challenges experienced by the SMEs. It pertains to overall transactions of a business that involves money. In financial, this will determine if the business is earning. Business owners really need to look after their financial status to know if there is a problem and avoid it.

The theme under the category production is sales. Sales pertains to a transaction made by people in which goods or services are exchanged for money. Sales are very important to a business to continue its production because in every move that a business makes money is involved. Regarding this, all the target participants of this study shared their thoughts. The Key Informant number 1 says, *“Oo tumaas din naman”* (Yes, it also increased), Key Informant number 2 *“Opo tumaas din naman po sales naming”* (Yes, our

sales have increased), Key Informant number 3 *“Oo kumikita kami ngayon”* (Yes we are making money now), Key Informant number 4 *“Oo sana may kita kaso kailangan na ng mga bata magtrabaho”* (Yes, we have sales but my children’s needs to work), Key Informant number 5 *“Oo tumaas talaga ang productivity o kita”* (Yes, productivity or income really increased). Attending different kind of training are beneficial to a business, it increases the chance of having more customers and sales. In today’s world of business there are competitors, the owner should make way on how to generate sales so he can pay his expenses and continues his business. Some of the business increase their sales but it suits only to the needs of their family. However, there is still a big chance to make more sales by using all the learnings gathered from the training attended. In business there are times that it makes them feel weak but at the end of the day they need to stand firm and face the upcoming days.

Moreover, Key Informant number 6 says, *“Oo naman kung wala kaming ibang gastusin malaki na talaga kita namin”* (Of course, if we do not have other expenses, we will have a lot of money), Key Informant number 7 *“Sa ngayon ok naman”* (For now it is okay), Key Informant number 8 *“Ngayon di ko masasabi na kumikita kami”* (Now I cannot say that we are making money), Key Informant number 9 *“Oo kumikita kami ng kaunti kesa dati”* (Yes, we earn a little more than before) and Key Informant number 10 *“Opo kumikita naman kami ng medjo malaki kesa dati”* (Yes, we earn a lot more than before). Like what mentioned above, there are times that the business sales are low but still the owner should not be discouraged to continue. In putting a business means that the owner knows the risks. The owner of a business should have courage to face all the problems that may arise. Putting up a business means taking all the risks to get customers, sales, and achieved goals.

In a business there are times that the owner of the business did not notice they are contributing to the success of our nation by simply helping people to get a job. Business today’s need to be strong for them to survive. Being knowledgeable on how to manage financial matter is an important part and the owner needs the skills to perform it well. Trainings upgrade their skills, makes them more knowledgeable and makes them prepared to face the life we have.

As stated above, based on their responses some of them are getting more sales because of the learnings they gained. But there are some of them that do not know if they earn more than before because of some personal issues they are facing. They said that their trainings in DTI really helps them and gives them the courage to continue their business.

According to the study of People Hum (2024) stated that training is the only way to expand the knowledge of all employees in a business. Many employers says that trainings are expensive, but it has a good impact in their business. Trainings allows employee to strengthen their skills and improve themselves. Employee will perform better and can work without the supervision of their employer.

The table in this area contains the significant statements of the small medium entrepreneurs (SMEs) after their training for SME Roving Academy.

Table 9
The theme on the Changes in the Lives of the Key Informants
along their Economic Aspects

Key Informants	Responses	Code	Theme
1.	“ <i>Oo tumaas din naman</i> ” (Yes, it also increased)		
2	“ <i>Opo tumaas din naman po sales naming</i> ” (Yes, our sales have increased)		
3	“ <i>Oo kumikita kami ngayon</i> ” (Yes we are making money now)		
4	“ <i>Oo sana may kita kaso kailangan na ng mga bata magtrabaho</i> ” (Yes, we have sales but my childrens needs to work)		
5	“ <i>Oo tumaas talaga ang productivity o kita</i> ” (Yes, productivity or income really increased)	Financial	Sales
6	“ <i>Oo naman kung wala kaming ibang gastusin malaki na talaga kita namin</i> ” (Of course, if we do not have other expenses, we eill have a lot of money)		
7	“ <i>Sa ngayon ok naman</i> ” (For now it is okay)		
8	“ <i>Ngayon di ko masasabi na kumikita kami</i> ” (Now I cannot say that we are making money)		
9	“ <i>Oo kumikita kami ng kaunti kesa dati</i> ” (Yes, we earn a little more than before)		
10	“ <i>Opo kumikita naman kami ng medjo malaki kesa dati</i> ” (Yes, we earn a lot more than before)		

Conclusions

Based on the findings, the following conclusions were drawn:

1. Majority of the SMEs’ respondents are under sole proprietorship, with 1 to 2 employees, currently in business operation for 3 to 5 years and with experience in selling products and services.
2. All of the survey questionnaire about the lived experience of the SMEs are interpreted that have strong effects on their competitive advantage and innovative system, financial matters, quality products with low manufacturing costs, helps give timely and relevant financial reports by looking at cost data, sales data, and revenue, contributes to reliable financial reports/statements for government monitoring and provides quality financial reports to trading partners/suppliers who extend credit. Moreover, all indicators along performance improvement are also developed such as provides budget and performance reports, enables the owners/managers to understand their tasks better and reduce uncertainty, speeds

up data collection, process, and storage of financial information, guides the business in deciding on their production capacities and inventory, provides timely recording of daily expenses for budget purposes, used in calculating lower costs and determining the income, assists the business in ensuring that appropriate human, machinery, and material resources, serves as an essential tool in issuing reliable financial data to evaluate expenses for cost allocation, and aids in analyzing the payment and estimating the personnel needed.

3. This study found out the reasons why the owner of the business is not able to continue his business because of some personal issues such as no one will be helping the owner in the production, conflict of interest, and the use of new technology as a means of new marketing strategy today.
4. The main problem of some of the SMEs in the implementation is the capital and materials and costly to maintain because of inadequate resources.
5. With thus, all of the SMEs who undergo training from the DTI Camarines Norte have problems in their production due to insufficient funds and some of them are lacking ideas on how to manage and maintain their businesses. Most of the businesses today complain about their poor sales and low number of customers because of their competitors. Some of them are first timer in field that is why they lacking those things and needs to be informed.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made considering the study's findings:

1. The Department of Trade and Industry may adapt information from the other country in providing trainings to businesses and;
2. The Department of Trade and Industry may allot more time in the screening of their program's recipients for them to have a better result. They may collaborate with the LGU and Barangay to know if their client whom to attend the training has the capacity to continue his business and are not after the kit materials only from the said department.
3. The Department of Trade and Industry may outsource cost-effective products or materials in their programs to lessen the burden in the part of small medium enterprise in their starting capital.
4. The Department of Trade and Industry may create a policy wherein they will continue to support the SMEs by providing them a financial help with a proper agreement with the SMEs that they will pay after they hit their goals.

5. The Department of Trade and Industry may increase cooperation and partnerships with government, private agencies, and educational institution for proper business handling and strategies. The LGU, BIR and educational institutions may work hand in hand to come up with activities that will cater to the needs of SMEs.
 6. Future researchers may conduct a study about the lived experiences of SMEs that will cater to their' needs in making quality products and services, effective and efficient financial information or statements and financial decision-making.
-

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study work attempted to reduce the risk of harm to the target respondents by ensuring the confidentiality of their responses and maintaining their identity throughout and after the research procedure. This researcher obtained their free, prior informed consent at the outset and promised them that they may withdraw from the study if necessary.

The study did not risk or injure people who were selected, as protocols were followed to obtain prior informed consent, ensuring voluntary participation, anonymity, and confidentiality of their responses.

Acknowledgements

The researcher would like to express his gratitude and thankfulness to the Almighty God for the many benefits that He has bestowed upon him during this study endeavor. He also expresses his profound appreciation to those individuals who, in some way or another, contributed to the completion of this study by providing moral, mental, and financial support. Without their assistance, the researcher would not have been able to finish this work.

Giving thanks, gratitude and appreciation to his adviser, Emmalyn C. Guaves, MBA; for providing him with essential advice during the whole process of this study. She instructed him on the approaches that should be used to carry out the study and to present the findings and details of the research in the most understandable manner. Her strength, vision, genuineness, and motivation have been a significant source of inspiration for him. Having the opportunity to learn under her guidance was both an honor and a wonderful experience.

He would like to express gratitude to the members of the panel of the thesis committee; Rusty G. Abanto, PhD, Professor V, Jennifer S. Rubio, PhD, Associate Professor V and Jefferson T. Dacer, CPA, MBA, Chief Administrative Officer for their support, advice, and insightful remarks.

The heads of offices of national government agencies who willingly complied with the requested data and permitted him to perform his research study to their respective offices and agencies. Those government employees of their respective national government agencies which served as the respondents, the researchers utmost appreciation. Without their willingness to share their precious time and providing honest responses, this research study will not be possible.

In addition, the researcher would like to express his gratitude to his close friends, colleagues, and loved ones for their love, support, encouragement, and inspiration. Their love and support were endless, and they are the strength that keep him at his toes even in complicated and difficult situations. They are his reinforcement in his tough moments and the driving force to keep him on waking, looking forward for another day.

REFERENCES

- Adams, K. (2023). 4 Reasons Why Building Customer Relationships is Especially Important Now. Octane AI. <https://www.octaneai.com/blog/customer-relationships>
- Asmuni, I. (2020). Reliability implementation of accounting information systems in improving small and medium enterprises financial performance. *Test Engineering and Management*, 83, 798-811. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341423378_Reliability_Implementation_of_Accounting_Information_Systems_in_Improving_Small_and_Medium_Enterprises_Financial_Performance
- Association of Southeast Asian Nations Development of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises in ASEAN (MSME) - ASEAN Main Portal
- Brown, J. (2020). Literature review Qualitative research methods and assumptions. [www.linkedin.com](https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/literature-review-qualitative-research-methods-jeff-brown-mba). <https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/literature-review-qualitative-research-methods-jeff-brown-mba>
- Bruce, E, Zhao, S., Egala, S.B., Mammet, Y., & Godson, K. (2022). Social Media and its Connection to Business Performance—A Literature Review. *American Journal of Industrial and Business Management*, 12(05), 877–893. <https://doi.org/10.4236/ajibm.2022.125045>
- Cirillo, E.M., Noro, J.E., & De Barros Neto, J.P. (2023). Management skills: The importance of academic training for entrepreneurs in micro, small and medium-sized enterprises. In Seven Editora eBooks. <https://doi.org/10.56238/ptoketheeducati-055>
- Das, P. (2023). The Importance Of Management In Business. Feedough. <https://www.feedough.com/importance-of-management-in-business/>
- Department of Budget and Management: Department of Trade and Industry dti (dbm.gov.ph)
- Department of Trade and Industry (2020). 2019 MSME statistics. <https://www.dti.gov.ph/resources/msme-statistics/>
- Department of Trade and Industry (2021). MSME Statistics | Department of Trade and Industry Philippines (dti.gov.ph)

- Department of Trade and Industry (2022). Supporting MSMEs in Rebuilding their business in the Philippines. <https://sdgs.un.org/sites/default/files/202205/Supporting%20MSMEs%20in%20Rebuilding%20their%20Business%20in%20the%20Philippines.pdf>
- Ellitan, L. (2021). The importance of entrepreneurship and information Technology for SMEs Strategic planning. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/352165438_The_Importance_of_Entrepreneurship_and_Information_Technology_for_SMEs_Strategic_Planning
- Faster Capital. (2023). The importance of capital in the early stages of a business venture - FasterCapital. <https://fastercapital.com/content/The-Importance-of-Capital-in-the-Early-Stages-of-a-Business-Venture.html>
- Haafte, R.V. (2023). Effect of customer satisfaction on profitability. <https://www.van-haafte.nl/customer-satisfaction/customer-satisfaction-models/83-effect-of-customer-satisfaction-on-profitability>
- Hansika, R. (2022). A comprehensive literature review on marketing strategies adopted by various industries. Social Science Research Network. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.4307660>
- Housing News Desks (2022). Capital and its importance for businesses. <https://housing.com/news/capital-and-its-importance-for-businesses/>
- Kronenberg, J., & Iida, N. (2011). Simple living and sustainable consumption. ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/286982246_Simple_Living_and_Sustainable_Consumption
- Lee, Y.C., Wang, Y. C., Lu, S. C., Hsieh, Y. F., Chien, C. H., Tsai, S. B., & Dong, W. (2016). An empirical research on customer satisfaction study: a consideration of levels of performance. *SpringerPlus*, 5(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40064-016-3208-z>
- Mbatha, Z., Moodley, M., & Nyika, F. (2023). Assessing the effectiveness of marketing strategies of Small to Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in Durban (South Africa). ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/374978134_Assessing_the_effectiveness_of_marketing_strategies_of_Small_to_Medium_Enterprises_SMEs_in_Durban_South_Africa
- National Economic Development Authority (2018). The Philippine development plan 2017-2022. [pdp.neda.gov.ph.https://pdp.neda.gov.ph/Philippinedevelopment-plan-2017-2022/](https://pdp.neda.gov.ph/Philippinedevelopment-plan-2017-2022/)
- Pearson, A. (2021). The importance of production planning in manufacturing. *Advanced*. <https://www.oneadvanced.com/news-and-opinion/the-importance-of-production-planning-in-manufacturing/>
- PeopleHum. (2024). The importance of training and development in the workplace | PeopleHum. <https://www.peoplehum.com/blog/the-importance-of-training-and-development-in-the-workplace#:~:text=The%20importance%20of%20training%20and%20development%20mostly%20revolves%20around%20programs,than%20immediate%20career%20role%20improvement.>
- Republic Act No. 9501, Official Gazette S. No. 1646 H. No. 1754 (2008). <https://www.officialgazette.gov.ph/2008/05/23/republic-act-no-9501>
- Resmi, S., Pahlevi, R.W., & Sayekti, F. (2021). Implementation of financial report and taxation training: performance of MSMEs in Special Regions Yogyakarta. *Jurnal*

Siasat Bisnis/Jurnal Siasat Bisnis, 25(1), 57–68. <https://doi.org/10.20885/jsb.vol25.iss1.art5>

- Rustiana, S., & Khairunnisa (2019). The effect of education level, business age and accounting knowledge on the implementation of SME accounting information systems in industrial era 4.0 (empirical study of MSME in South Tangerang). *KnE Social Sciences*, 3(26), 872–887. <https://doi.org/10.18502/kss.v3i26.5420>
- Sa'adah, V.U., Mugiono, N., & Susilowati, C. (2023). The impact of corporate image and relationship marketing on customer loyalty in mediated customer satisfaction at SMEs. *International Journal of Research in Business and Social Science*, 12(7), 126–135. <http://doi.org/10.20525/ijrbs.v12i7.2878>
- Somwethee, P., Aujirapongpan, S., & Ru-Zhue, J. (2023). The influence of entrepreneurial capability and innovation capability on sustainable organization performance: Evidence of community enterprise in Thailand. *Journal of Open Innovation: Technology, Market, and Complexity*, 9(2), 100082. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.joitmc.2023.100082>
- Yimam, M.H. (2022). Impact of training on employee's performance: A case study of Bahir Dar University, Ethiopia. *Cogent Education*, 9(1). <https://doi.org/10.1080/2331186x.2022.2107301>